

The Social Life of Algorithms: Tracing notions of algorithms beyond human-algorithm interactions

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Abstract. This paper examines how the social meaning, agency and potentials of algorithms in everyday life are challenging the technical notions of algorithms that are embedded in their design. Although tensions between social and technical aspects of algorithms have been explored in critical algorithm studies, there remains a research gap regarding the integration of algorithms into social discourse, material culture, local practices, and imaginaries. Building on the concept of *social life* the paper traces how notions of algorithms are negotiated, imagined and re-interpreted within the context of social interactions as the Bitcoin Beach project is integrated into everyday life of people in the Salvadorian town of El Zonte. The findings presented in this paper contribute to extending ethnographies of algorithms beyond human-algorithm interactions by exploring the various contexts in which algorithms are constructed and scrutinising what is at stake when notions of algorithms become social by design.

Keywords: HCI, human-algorithm, design anthropology

1 Introduction

In recent years, HCI researchers aligned with the emergent field of critical algorithm studies have increasingly adopted anthropological lenses to position the interactions between humans and algorithm-driven technologies as the sites where the concept of an algorithm becomes appropriated [Kitchin, 2017]. The move from human-computer interactions to human-algorithm interactions seeks to pay closer attention to how bottom-up notions of the meaning, agency and potential of algorithms can inform a more contextual understanding of the everyday impact of algorithmic technologies, interfaces and services [Gran et al., 2021; Seaver, 2018, 2017]. To support this transition, a growing number of researchers are demonstrating how people construct diverse notions of the meaning, agency and potential of the concept of *an algorithm* through gossip, folk theories, diverse forms of anthropomorphization and imaginaries that emerge from everyday uses of algorithm-driven technologies rather than from knowledge of their technical properties.

While ethnographic approaches in critical algorithm studies contribute to broadening how the concept of an algorithm can be understood, they rely on the perceived duration,

quality and outcome of specific human-algorithm interactions. In doing so, emerging notions of algorithms become entangled with the technologies that allow humans and algorithms to interact. In contrast, scarce attention has been placed on developing methods to examine how people make sense of algorithms outside the spatial and temporal boundaries where humans and algorithms interact. By relying on samples made from those who (can afford to) experience human-algorithm interactions, current approaches in critical algorithm studies risk limiting the analysis to a one-dimensional understanding of how the concept of an algorithm becomes appropriated, and to what consequences.

To address this gap in research towards an ethnography of algorithms in everyday life, we examine the transition from technical to social understandings of the meaning, agency and potential of algorithms through the lens of the social life of things: a conceit proposed by Appadurai [1988] to place attention on the diverse situations and practices that imbue meaning to things that inherently have none. Through this lens, we extend the reach of critical algorithm approaches and examine how notions of algorithms are discussed, negotiated and adopted outside interactions with technology, focusing instead on interactions with other notions of algorithms and the ideals and values attached to them. In doing so, we shift attention to the everyday situations and practices where, even though algorithm-driven technologies are not in sight, notions of algorithms continue to be discussed, imagined and re-interpreted, and ask:

- How are everyday practices shaping notions of algorithms?
- How are notions of algorithms transforming everyday practices?
- How are notions of algorithms mediating the perception and adoption of algorithm-driven technologies?

This late-breaking paper presents findings from field research in the Salvadorian town of El Zonte, where the foreign-led Bitcoin Beach project aims to transition the local population into a sustainable Bitcoin economic ecosystem by promoting the adoption of, as the project frames it, the *Bitcoin algorithm*. Building on multi-sited theory [Marcus, 1995] and methods from design anthropology [Smith et al., 2016; Gunn et al., 2013], we traced how, when and where notions of the *Bitcoin algorithm* are becoming embedded with different—often opposing—ideals and potentials as the Bitcoin Beach project continues to be implemented and contested.

The following sections provide empirical accounts detailing how notions of the *Bitcoin algorithm* became social, and opens a conversation regarding the feedback-loop between the construction of these notions and the transformation of the practices where notions emerge. We begin by positioning the social life of algorithms in relation to current approaches in HCI and critical algorithm studies. After a brief introduction to El Zonte and the ambitions of the Bitcoin Beach project, we follow how notions of the *Bitcoin algorithm* become social by connecting the experiences of different members of the community. We end with a discussion of the opportunities for approaching algorithms through the lens of *social life*, the tensions that arise when notions of

algorithms are constructed alongside everyday practices, and the implications of purposefully curating top-down notions of algorithms.

2 HCI and the social life of algorithms

Emerging critical approaches in the broader field of HCI were characterised by challenging the dominant narratives and discourses around the impact of algorithm-driven technologies, paying close attention to the broader political and economic implications and unintended outcomes of algorithmic systems. In doing so, early research shaping the field of critical algorithm studies often overlapped with critical data and critical media studies [Kitchin and Lauriault, 2014] as the three areas studied the impact of algorithms at a systemic scale by quantifying the results of unintended outcomes rather than by understanding how the behaviour of algorithms is perceived and experienced contextually. Some of this early research includes the themes of algorithmic bias and discrimination [Noble, 2018; Eubanks, 2016], the politics of algorithmic transparency, accountability, explainability and interpretability [Mittelstadt et al., 2019; Pasquale, 2015; Diakopoulos, 2015], how algorithms reinforce and amplify existing social inequalities, particularly concerning race, gender, and class [Ruha, 2020], how algorithms can systematically discriminate against marginalised communities [Kleinberg, 2018; Sandvig et. al., 2014], as well as a more critical approach to the use of machine learning algorithms that focus attention on their social and political implications [Crawford and Calo, 2016].

To distance themselves from critical data and critical media studies, researchers in critical algorithm studies began to adopt ethnographic methods to engage with the everyday experiences of people with algorithm-driven technologies [Gillespie, 2014]. Kitchin and Dodge [2014] first hinted at studying the lives of algorithms by proposing a research agenda that looks at the feedback loop between algorithmic systems and their users, raising concerns about the capacity of algorithms to mediate information and shape everyday practices. Similarly, around the time when critical approaches to algorithms were becoming established in HCI research, Dourish, although not directly, pointed out to Appadurai's approach by stating that "*the limits of the term algorithm are determined by social engagements rather than by technological or material constraints*" [Dourish, 2016]. By placing the focus on the social and cultural contexts where algorithmic systems are deployed [Seaver, 2018], researchers have begun to pay closer attention to how these systems are implemented and experienced by both professionals [Ruckenstein and Granroth, 2020] and laypeople [Gillespie, 2018].

As the move towards understanding and documenting public perceptions of algorithms grows stronger, researchers increasingly shift attention away from code and into human-algorithm interactions where people make sense of code. The move from technical to cultural notions of algorithms is relevant because, although from a technical perspective, the term algorithm has historically referred to a rigorous set of (mathematical) instructions used for calculations and problem-solving, research in

social sciences and humanities has shown that, over time, the concept of *an algorithm* has been subject to varied interpretations—from the magical and mythical to the anthropomorphic—that are continually transformed alongside the contexts and purposes in which algorithms are deployed [Cave et al., 2020]

To encounter emerging notions of algorithms, research in critical algorithm studies has relied primarily on building from people's experiences while using algorithm-driven services and technologies to reverse engineer how their notions of algorithms became constructed. In doing so, researchers aim to provide empirical accounts of how people build relationships with algorithmic systems and how these relationships can shape how users approach algorithm-driven technologies. Some of these approaches include algorithmic folk theories as a method to collect lay understandings of algorithms that are constructed due to negative or positive experiences with algorithmic platforms [Eslami et al., 2016], stories about algorithms [Schellewald, 2022] and algorithmic gossip [Bishop, 2019] as methods to document shared ideas of algorithms by users of the same platform, algorithmic personas as a method to visualise algorithmic functions through stereotypical human characters [Büchi, 2021], a 'decoding' of algorithms as an approach to studying the relationships that people experience with algorithms [Lomborg and Kapsch, 2020], and algorithmic imaginaries as an approach to capture what algorithms mean for people in the intersection of use, gossip and reflection [Bucher, 2017].

The ethnographic turn in critical algorithm studies has been central to highlighting the relevance of context both for researching how notions of algorithms are constructed and for broadening how the impact of algorithms can be understood and studied. Nevertheless, while providing rich accounts of emergent notions of algorithms, the reliance on human-algorithm interactions as the sites where humans become aware of algorithms leaves out of sight the myriad social and cultural practices where notions of algorithms are socialised, negotiated and adopted. To approach these practices as research sites, the analysis needs to account for how the ideals and values embedded in (the design of) algorithms influence how people talk about, explain, introduce, and imagine algorithms as part of everyday life.

The view that things—such as stones, trees, trinkets and algorithms—have a social life aims to place attention on the diverse situations and practices that imbue meaning to things that inherently have none. Kopytoff [1986] first proposed the concept of *object biographies* to emphasise the need to examine the entire life cycle of objects—through production, exchange and consumption—as a method for understanding that the meanings attached to an object are dependent on the people and events to which it is connected. The social life of things [Appadurai, 1988] is a conceit to further the notion that the transactions that enable the exchange of things are invested with the ideals and values of social relations. By focusing on how relationships between objects and people are constructed over time, the essays collected by Appadurai show that objects are not static, inert things. Instead, they are part of dynamic social and cultural networks where things can be used to express and reinforce cultural values, traditions and social

hierarchies. As a result, *things* can be used to maintain or shift power relations and create new cultural practices and identities.

The term *algorithm*, therefore, can be said to have a social life, collecting and shedding varied ideals and values as the term is appropriated and scrutinised across diverse practices of everyday life. In the following sections, we provide an overview of the theory and methods we used to operationalise the lens of *social life* as a framework for extending critical algorithm approaches outside the spatial and temporal boundaries of human-computer interactions, expanding the sites where notions of algorithms are constructed, and scrutinising what is at stake when notions of algorithms become social by design.

3 Research design

This late-breaking research discusses early findings from an eight weeks ethnographic study of the social life of the Bitcoin algorithm in the Salvadorian town of El Zonte. To research the social life of the Bitcoin algorithm empirically, we prototyped ethnographic methods based on design anthropology and multi-sited theory. Multi-sited theory [Marcus, 1995] is an approach for researching social phenomena that cannot be accounted for by focusing on a single site, such as following the construction of a metaphor or a story and the cultural transformations taking place as they become socialised and adopted. It is relevant to highlight that, In a multi-sited research approach, the concept of the site is understood as the object of study, not the context of study. From this perspective, the negotiations that take place as notions of algorithms are socialised and scrutinised become the sites of research.

To encounter these sites, we prototyped ethnographic methods through the lens of design anthropology. Design anthropology is a theoretical and methodological approach that explores the cultural phenomena that emerge in everyday life by moving beyond traditional ethnographic methods, which rely primarily on observation and reflection, to actively involve research participants in co-creating knowledge [Smith and Kjærsgaard, 2015; Rabinow, 2008]. Design anthropology is relevant to support the study of the social life of things as it provides an interdisciplinary, future-oriented approach to studying, documenting, and understanding the beliefs, tensions, power relations and feedback loops that hold together the relationships between people and *things* and how these relationships are shaped by social, cultural, and historical contexts [Tunstall, 2020].

By combining design anthropology and multi-sited theory, we engaged 20 residents from El Zonte with different affiliations and positions towards the Bitcoin Beach project. More specifically, these accounts belong to participants from two age groups that are indicative of the positionality of participants. One group corresponds to the 20 to 35 years old members of the community socialising a singular notion of the Bitcoin algorithm. The second group represents the 45 and over segment of the population who

are going through the process of negotiating multiple notions of the Bitcoin algorithm. Some of these methods included participants mapping where gossip [Dunbar, 2004] concerning the meaning, agency and potential of the Bitcoin algorithm emerges across the town and its surroundings, positioning the influence and positionality of different notions of the Bitcoin algorithm in relation to social learning strategies [Bandura, 1977], and graphing reciprocity [Mauss, 2005] in relation to shared expectations regarding adopting the ideals embedded in the Bitcoin algorithm.

We also relied on traditional methods such as graphic elicitation [Varga-Atkins and O'Brien, 2009] and directed storytelling [Thomson, 1999] to access concepts, feelings, and imaginaries that are hard to put into words. This interdisciplinary approach allowed us to position the participant's recollections of memories and anecdotes as research sites for unpacking individual and shared notions of the Bitcoin algorithm and the practices being transformed alongside them.

In the following sections, we introduce accounts of ideals and notions of the *Bitcoin algorithm* collected during mapping sessions in the town of El Zonte and during the Adopting Bitcoin Conference held in San Salvador in November of 2022. We use these accounts to trace the social life of the *Bitcoin algorithm* from its inception by the hand of the Bitcoin Beach project leadership to its adoption and contestation by different members of the community in El Zonte. The accounts are pseudonymised to preserve the age range of participants as indicative of positionality.

4 El Zonte as a test site for the *Bitcoin algorithm*

El Zonte is a small coastal town in the country of El Salvador—just a few unpaved roads wide on both sides of a small stream—about one hour away from the capital city. For many decades, people in El Zonte—like most other communities in El Salvador—lived in relative isolation from foreign interests due to the country's political, economic and social insecurities. However, in the early 2000s, before El Salvador began to reform its image and invest in attracting foreign tourism and investment, El Zonte had already begun to make a name for itself thanks to the surfing conditions that can be found around the town. This resulted in foreign tourism slowly coming to El Zonte, gradually introducing the community to ideas and ideals of what a different life could or should look like. By 2010, the community started seeing Salvadorian investors coming into town to build accommodations to support local tourism, which in the last years has been doubled by foreign developers as a result of a growing sense of security in living and investing in the country. These days, the people of El Zonte interact daily with foreigners. Most of its residents between 18 and 35 speak English fluently—with many working hospitality jobs—and a growing number of expats are residing in the area.

Nonetheless, until 2019 the town had a precarious physical and digital infrastructure, and it was far from having a thriving tourism industry. Things rapidly changed with the arrival of the Bitcoin Beach project, the first of a growing number of initiatives

worldwide aimed at transforming small communities, mostly in developing countries, into Bitcoin circular economies. El Zonte was chosen as the context to explore the adoption of Bitcoin because it offered both a local community with a lack of economic, technological and educational opportunities and a growing foreign community interested in investing in the town because of its tourism potential. During its first years, the project was mainly discussed amongst Bitcoin enthusiasts. However, the ambitions of the Bitcoin Beach project became internationally known seemingly overnight as El Salvador’s president announced that the country would be adopting Bitcoin as a legal tender at the end of 2021. The news sparked worldwide interest, an influx of tourism and the necessary momentum to hold the first Bitcoin conference in El Salvador.

While attending the 2022 Adopting Bitcoin Conference in San Salvador, it became apparent that the Bitcoin Beach project is more than just allowing people in El Zonte to have digital currency and pay for services and subscriptions that otherwise they could not access: *“Bitcoin is a way of life,”* as speakers and participants, most of which are in their late 20s and early 30s, are quick to share. The approach to Bitcoin—a blockchain-supported cryptocurrency—as an analogy to discuss how people approach everyday life is scaffolded by the diverse principles and ideals that have been associated with Bitcoin and blockchain technology since the appearance of the white paper anonymously written in 2008 under the pseudonym of Satoshi Nakamoto [2008]. However, the anonymity of the key figure behind Bitcoin, as well as the decentralised nature of the technology—where there is no legally recognised authority that can say which principles and ideals align better with Satoshi’s vision—has resulted in the use and potential of Bitcoin to be open for interpretation. As a conference speaker puts it: *“The only way to control the narrative is by becoming a relevant voice in the community.”*

5 Tracing the social life of the *Bitcoin algorithm*

The following subsections examine four stages in the social life of the Bitcoin algorithm. We begin by tracing the ideals that became attached to the concept and continue by scrutinising the strategy behind their socialisation. Once we have identified how these ideals are curated and socialised, we focus on the tensions and transformation that arise as notions of the Bitcoin algorithm are negotiated alongside everyday practices. We end by unpacking how members of the community contest top-down ideals by reflecting on potential changes to their everyday practices.

5.1 Curating the ideals of the Bitcoin algorithm

Bitcoin Beach aims to become a relevant voice in guiding how the potential and purpose of Bitcoin are understood and implemented, and El Zonte was the first step in prototyping how to talk about Bitcoin in order to encourage adoption; now, there are dozens of similar projects aiming to transition entire communities into adopting Bitcoin

as a currency and a way of life. A member of the Bitcoin Beach leadership explains that:

We are an ideology, a way of living life through the ideals that Bitcoin represents, but the technical side of things is too...well, technical! No one sells these [algorithm-driven] services to regular folks by explaining how their maths work, but what we can do is take leverage how algorithms are perceived in mainstream media, like smart, sleek, connected, modern and so on, and use those ideals to paint a picture of the Bitcoin algorithm that people in El Zonte can relate to.

For the Bitcoin Beach project, the *Bitcoin algorithm* embodies ideals of efficiency, inclusivity and modernity. These values were picked amongst other popular ones within the Bitcoin community—such as trustworthy, clean, incorruptible and truthful—because of their higher chance to resonate with the community of El Zonte. Another member of the Bitcoin Beach leadership adds that:

If I have to explain the Bitcoin algorithm to some wealthy guy back home [in Canada], I will probably have to use other values because he won't be so excited about efficiency and modernity because he probably experiences those anyway. Instead, he probably is more excited about concepts like trustworthy and incorruptible...My point is that the Bitcoin algorithm can do many things, but we need to be strategic about the ones we highlight based on the context and people we are working with.

Although using ideals and values in the design of algorithms has become a common practice, such as in popular frameworks like fairness accountability and transparency (FAT), responsible AI, and human-centred AI, the ideals imbued to the *Bitcoin algorithm* were chosen based on their likeness to become adopted and promoted by the people of El Zonte. Consequently, the early success of the Bitcoin Beach project depends largely on the community of El Zonte adopting these ideals.

The ideals of the *Bitcoin algorithm* are first introduced to the community of El Zonte within the walls of Hope House, the headquarters of Bitcoin Beach. There, Bitcoin Beach offers free education and capacitation about Bitcoin and how to *evangelise*—as the practice is referred to by Bitcoiners—others in the community. The target demographic consists mainly of the 20 to 30 years old native residents of El Zonte who, in recent years, have become exponentially exposed to the worldviews of tourists and expats, many of whom support the vision of the Bitcoin Beach project. The recruiting of Bitcoin promoters is done by core members of the project. Alan, a native of El Zonte in his mid-30s who has been working as a recruiter since the early days of Bitcoin Beach, explains that:

The younger generations of El Zonte are much more aligned with the values we believe in than the older ones. They want the kind of lifestyle that has become associated with algorithms, you know, fast, sleek, clean, shiny, efficient...they might not know what algorithms are or how they work, but they are aware of the hype around them, and they want to be a part of it...everyone wants to live in the future, and we are bringing that future to El Zonte.

People who complete training at Hope House become Bitcoin promoters, tasked with encouraging both business owners and the community at large to embrace the social and cultural transformations that Bitcoin Beach seeks to achieve. Recruiting business owners is necessary to support a circular Bitcoin economy through Bitcoin Beach services and takes place mostly at their place of business, such as restaurants, hotels, and convenience stores. On the other hand, recruiting other community members is a strategy to spread the ideals of the Bitcoin algorithm outside the relational, spatial and temporal boundaries where humans and algorithms interact.

5.2 Socialising the ideals of the Bitcoin algorithm

While the Bitcoin Beach project socialises ideals of efficiency, inclusivity and modernity to drive adoption of the Bitcoin algorithm, modernity and efficiency resonate the most amongst Bitcoin promoters and their peers. El Zonte—despite the influx of money and tourism in the last five years—is mostly run-down houses and restaurants, poorly-kept dirt roads, and not much to do for the local residents in their 20s. The new hotels and restaurants that cater to foreign Bitcoin and surf enthusiasts stand in contrast with what the town had offered until recently, and Bitcoin advertisements, stickers and graffiti have become part of the fabric of the town, turning otherwise unremarkable spaces, like trash cans and electricity poles, into postcards of the Bitcoin Beach project.

When asked about the sudden appearance of Bitcoin (Beach) propaganda, promoters agree that they appreciate seeing signs of Bitcoin everywhere because it reminds them of the ideals they are working hard to instil in the everyday life of people. Yet, the contrast between these ideals and the everyday reality of El Zonte has led to promoters becoming more critical of what they see and encounter as they go about their daily life in El Zonte. Yenny, a 25 years old resident of El Zonte and one of the first to become a promoter, shares that:

We [the promoters] are more perceptive now, to...you know, things that need to change. Before, we would just see things and be like [shrugging]; it's just how things are. But now, when we are waiting in line because the old guy [the shop owner] is counting pennies and doing maths to give change, we know it doesn't have to be that way. That he could be more efficient, that we could have more time to do our things if others were more efficient.

These reflections are common amongst promoters as they discuss ideals like efficiency and modernity in relation to changing daily practices and behaviours that, in their views, would benefit the community. Promoters share that they often find themselves discussing the potential of the *Bitcoin algorithm* and its values when doing things *the old way*, such as collecting wood and cooking with fire, taking the bus for 30 minutes to pay for basic services, or doing laundry by hand. Jerson, a recently trained promoter in his early 20s, shares:

I see a different version of myself when I think through these values—a sort of algorithmic version of myself that encourages me to be more efficient, smarter,

sophisticated. And we [the promoters] feel a responsibility to help others realise how things can change for the best if they apply the ideals of the Bitcoin algorithm to the things they do.

While embodying the ideals embedded in the Bitcoin algorithm might sound abstract, for promoters, it is no different to embodying ideals such as solidarity and humility as part of embracing the teachings of the local church. Maura, one of the few promoters over 30, explains that:

The community in El Zonte is very religious, and when people are discussing a challenge or wrongdoing, it is common to encourage others to see themselves in the light of scripture, like, making those ideals part of how you approach life and all that stuff. So we are doing the same thing, except we want them to see themselves in the light of the Bitcoin algorithm.

Evangelising the community is widely seen as part of the social contract of being part of the Bitcoin (Beach) community, and promoters are encouraged to use any opportunity to nudge the community into associating the ideals of Bitcoin Beach with positive changes in their day-to-day life. Mateo, a 30 years old recruiter, describes that:

The job of the promoters is to convert the community. You know, the 'orange pill' thing, and they do it by telling others that adopting Bitcoin is not only about digital payments or having access to more services or whatever, but that the Bitcoin algorithm embodies the ideals needed to become a modern, digital and future-thinking community. If the community adopts our ideals first, they will not question adopting our services later...so spreading our ideals is a priority. We need the community to be aligned with the kind of transformation we want to see.

While promoters are eager to embrace new ideals as a means to trigger changes to everyday practices, those in the community who are new to the concept of *an algorithm* are faced with negotiating change against little information. To encourage the older generations to visualise the person they can become if they apply the principles of the *Bitcoin algorithm* to everyday decisions, behaviours and practices, promoters often approach them while performing everyday tasks that could be transformed through the services and ideals of Bitcoin. These tasks range from paying bills and shopping for groceries, cooking and cleaning in their homes, or taking walks to collect wood and shells. As a result, people are beginning to make sense of the meaning, agency and potential of the *Bitcoin algorithm* based on how they imagine these practices transforming if they were to embrace the ideals of efficiency and modernity.

5.3 Negotiating the ideals of the Bitcoin algorithm

To unpack how different members of the community make sense of the meaning, agency and potential of the Bitcoin algorithm, this subsection provides extended accounts of three ongoing negotiations unfolding alongside everyday practices.

The first negotiation is between Mila, a promoter in her early 20s, and her 65 years old uncle, Antonio, who owns and runs a small stall in town.

Mila: My uncle has a little stall on one of the side roads. He sells just a few things, cheap stuff for kids and some grains and flour, pencils, and things like that. But he is also the only one that sells sim cards, so tourists are always going there to top-up their phones...oh and he also has a few old slot machines on the side and sells beer...cheap beer! So it can get busy at times! It sounds good, but there is often a long line, and locals are used to it, but you can see tourists get frustrated, and sometimes they just leave or will not come back to buy beer from him because they know it's slow. You see, he [the uncle] likes to talk to people, which is good for him perhaps but not good for business. So I am pushing hard to get him to stop chatting and focus on giving better service to tourists. A Bitcoin terminal will not be enough to keep tourists coming, he needs to embrace efficiency.

Antonio: She [her niece] is so concerned with time and money since these [Bitcoin Beach] people started coming. Efficiency here and there all the time! That my shelves don't look modern, sell this instead of that, don't chat at work, chat later, bla bla. I know she wants to help, but I have a stall to talk to people, not to make money. They [the promoters] talk about efficiency as if we didn't know the concept [laughing], but I am an old man, and talking to my friends all day feels like an efficient use of the time I have left!...So their ideas of efficiency are definitely not the same as mine.

As the ideals of the *Bitcoin algorithm* become subject to scrutiny, different understandings of efficiency and modernity begin to be formed and attached to new interpretations of the meaning, agency and potential of the *Bitcoin algorithm*. Such is the outcome between the negotiations of Gladys, a convenience store owner in her early 60s who adopted Bitcoin in 2021 and remains one of the few active Bitcoin users over 50, and Laura, a close friend of hers who remains sceptical of the benefits of adopting Bitcoin.

Gladys: I have had this [convenience] store for more than 15 years now. People trust me; I have fair prices and good products. Business is good, I like being a shop owner, but I never liked handling cash. It's messy, it's scary...you know, things were different [less safe] just until a few years ago, so having cash lying around was never to my liking. So when the kids [the promoters] started telling me about this Bitcoin thing and that people would pay with their phones and I would not have to deal with cash, I was intrigued! They said it would be more efficient and quick, instant...like magic! And that the shop would look nicer and modern if I have these terminals and screens and stuff, so it would attract more tourists. So I gave it a try, and it took me some time to get used to it, but I love it now! So now I barely accept cash anymore, only from people I trust, but [laughing] I am still trying to get my friends to sign up so they stop bringing me cash!

Laura: Oh, you spoke with Gladys? Let me tell you something, we are good friends, but we almost got into a big fight over this Bitcoin algorithm crap because we [Laura and her friends] don't think she thought this [adopting Bitcoin] through. Our whole thing was sending the kids in the morning to buy some candy to get them out of the house and give us some space. But now she [Gladys] is not accepting cash, so now none of us can get the kids out of the house anymore! So I'm sitting at home taking care of my grandchildren, and I'm just thinking, damn, this Bitcoin thing!... I'm not mad at her anymore, but I'm mad at those Bitcoin people because they don't seem to understand how things work here. They just think their ways are more efficient because they come from [air quotes] more developed countries? This Bitcoin algorithm is just like the gringos that come looking to take things away from us and pretend they are helping...you tell me, modernity for whom are we talking about?

A similar situation occurs as Maria, a promoter in her late 20s, tries to onboard 50 years old Teresa, who runs one of the few remaining locally-owned restaurants in town, which is also one of the last restaurants using wood for cooking meals.

Maria: I explained to her that I understood why they cook with an open fire and that I know that gas is expensive and wood is freely available. But I also explained to her that if she switched to gas, she could serve more customers because she could cook faster because gas is more efficient than fire. I also said I knew that waiting for the [gas] truck can be inconvenient, but that with Bitcoin she can now buy gas online and get it delivered without any hassle. I explained to her that the Bitcoin algorithm makes these things possible, that it allows you to be more efficient and take less time doing chores so that you can have more time to do other things. I also pointed out that the restaurant would look nicer and more modern with a nice gas stove, Bitcoin terminals, etc. And that the only thing that would change for her is that her life would be easier. She was not interested...I mean! [shrugging in disbelief] I think it's just because they want to go against things they don't understand as old people do.

Teresa: Well, I didn't think much about [the Bitcoin algorithm] before. I am not interested in those things, and I don't entertain gossip, so all I can say is that I don't know how it works, but it makes me nervous that they talk so much about becoming something we are not by adopting these [air quotes] ideals as they call them....And that is a problem because what Maria doesn't want to understand or even believe is that I like cooking with fire. It is how my mother taught me, and it makes food more tasty. And it keeps me engaged with what I am doing; fire is unpredictable, it tests you as a cook...anyone can cook with gas! People come to my restaurant because I cook with care, not with time in mind. I also enjoy looking for wood. It is my private time for thinking, and sometimes I invite people to join me, and we chat and gossip. Switching to gas would take all these experiences and memories away! I wish they [the promoters] were more in tune with our ideals, like, what happens to tradition when everything has to become modern?

As the ideals attached to the *Bitcoin algorithm* become increasingly negotiated alongside everyday practices, a growing number of people in the community are resenting the pressure to change that is socialised as part of adopting the ideals of efficiency and modernity. These tensions are giving rise to notions of the *Bitcoin algorithm* that stand in opposition to those first set into a social path inside the rooms of Hope House.

5.4 Contesting the ideals of the Bitcoin algorithm

The inclination towards contestation emerges from two converging factors. On the one hand, many members of the community, particularly those over the age of 40, are growing wary of promoters constantly approaching them during routine chores and everyday practices to encourage them to adopt the ideals of the Bitcoin algorithm. On the other hand, the same segment of the population—as a result of growing up more deprived of technology and infrastructure—has a stronger connection to the backdrop of El Zonte: the Pacific Ocean, rough waves, volcanic sand, rocky cliffs and thick vegetation. This convergence has led to a growing number of people weighing the ideals of the Bitcoin algorithm against the values and memories that being close to nature evokes in them.

Mayte, a childhood friend of Teresa, shares that when being by themselves with nature, they are inspired to share memories and anecdotes of growing up in El Zonte and reflect on how quickly things have changed in the last ten years. While the community generally appreciates the influx of tourism, there are issues of displacement, water scarcity and inflation that have transformed and, in many ways, affected how they live. Consequently, the sudden arrival of the Bitcoin Beach project and the rapid transformations taking place as a result make many in the community uneasy. Raul, a local surf instructor in his mid-40s, describes how he came to challenge the ideal of efficiency by thinking about how the sand on the beach is constantly in motion, being renewed by the tides and shaping the waves in turn. This reflection led him to conclude that nature is not efficient, it is consistent, and if you study the cycles, you can engage nature meaningfully instead of efficiently.

Lynda and Juan, who have been fishing in the area since childhood, are suspicious of ideas of efficiency and what it can do to their way of life. Juan explains he wishes he could sit down with the algorithm, have a beer and understand why efficiency and modernity are so important to "it". Lynda complains that people in El Zonte do not even know what the *Bitcoin algorithm* looks like and that people cannot negotiate with something they can't touch or see. Juan argues:

Juan argues: *We can touch the sand, the ocean, we can feel the rain, we can connect to the sensations and memories that these experiences generate and put them in the balance against those that this algorithm is supposed to give us...[gesticulating, looking around and making pfft sound] nothing!*

Lynda ends with an analogy: *If you stay too long in the fishing boat you'll forget how to swim, so when you rod brakes you'll starve because you've forgotten how*

to dive and spear. I understand that fishing with a rod is more efficient, but what about the things you lose in exchange?

Others in the community are relying on similar experiences and memories of different times to make sense of how they feel about the ideals being socialised by promoters. It is during these moments of reflection in nature that, increasingly, members of the community find themselves scrutinising the meaning, agency and potential of algorithms and constructing alternative notions of the Bitcoin algorithm. As the pressure to adopt the ideals and services of Bitcoin Beach grow, these experiences give members of the community a safe space to contextualise, imagine, and, if needed, contest the ideals and transformations that the *Bitcoin algorithm* might bring, not only to their everyday practices but to how they approach the present and think about the future.

While promoters were prompted to reflect on the *Bitcoin beach* algorithm when performing practices directly associated with the perceived benefits of Bitcoin, such as paying for goods and services, older members of the community are triggered by practices that are further removed from the physical infrastructure of Bitcoin, such as collecting wood or fishing, as these practices remind them of what is at stake if they embrace the ideals of the *Bitcoin algorithm*. Consequently, promoters are more likely to attach positive implications to adopting Bitcoin as a currency and way of life, while the older generations are more prone to attach negative ones.

6 Discussion

Through the lens of social life, we traced how notions of algorithms are constructed in El Zonte, from being curated and strategically socialised, to being negotiated and contested in relation to the practices that the ideals embedded in the *Bitcoin algorithm* aim to transform. We discuss our findings in the following subsections.

6.1 The social life of algorithms

Approaching notions of algorithms through the lens of *social life* allowed us to demonstrate that both notions of algorithms and positions towards algorithm-driven technologies can be constructed alongside daily practices that transcend the relational, spatial and temporal boundaries of human-algorithm interactions. More so, our findings indicate that emerging notions of algorithms are largely defined by the practices that trigger reflection about the meaning, agency and potential of algorithms. A design anthropological account of the social life of algorithms provided us with a framework to identify new sites of research where we documented tensions, negotiations and transformations that would have remained hidden if we had conducted our research in traditional sites such as Hope House and the business being onboarded.

These findings suggest that current approaches in critical algorithm studies could benefit from tracing the origins and spreading patterns of algorithmic gossip, folk theories and imaginaries as a means to extend how we understand what classifies as an everyday experience of people with algorithm-driven technologies. Positioning ethnographic methods in these new sites can shorten the gap in critical algorithms studies concerning the everyday social and cultural factors that pressure notions of algorithms into being, such as the distance that notions of algorithms can travel, which everyday practices lead to higher rates of adoption or rejection, and the role of ideals and values in shaping how people make sense of algorithms.

6.2 Notions of algorithms and changing practices

In addition, by relying on multi-sited theory to follow how the concept of the *Bitcoin algorithm* is curated, socialised, negotiated and contested, we show how everyday practices and notions of algorithms continually shape each other, leading to the embedding of new meanings, agency and potentials not only to emerging notions of algorithms but to everyday practices.

On the one hand, these findings contribute to research in critical algorithm studies showing how the social, cultural and political context must be accounted for when scrutinising public notions of the impact and potential of algorithms. On the other hand, the capacity of algorithmic gossip, folk theories and imaginaries to pressure change raises new questions concerning how emerging notions of algorithms are given agency by those who construct or adopt them and how these shape the power dynamics of human-algorithm relationships.

While studying the social life of algorithms allows to empirically study the theoretical approaches of Kitchin and Dodge [2014] and Dourish [2016], additional research concerning the coevolutionary dynamics between everyday practices and emerging notions of algorithms would benefit from engaging participants during a longer timeframe and limiting the study to a single practice undergoing transformations. In the context of El Zonte, this could be the transition from cooking with fire to cooking with gas or the fading out of cash as payment in a local business. A more focused approach would still benefit from a social life approach as a strategy to identify stakeholders, narratives and adjacent sites that pressure the feedback loop.

6.3 Floating narratives

In the context of El Zonte, rationalising the concept of an algorithm through a set of curated ideals resulted in people developing different and often contrasting notions of the agency and potential of algorithms. These notions rapidly led to members of the community transforming their practices and beliefs to accommodate the potentials and fears imbued in the Bitcoin algorithm, many of which were transformed to embrace the use of the services provided by Bitcoin Beach. These transformations suggest that purposefully curating and mobilising a specific set of ideals alongside the deployment of

algorithm-driven technologies provides a strategy to mediate the negotiation, contestation and appropriation not only of these technologies but of the concept of an algorithm and the benefits or harms it can bring to people, regardless of their interactions with these technologies.

Although we need to replicate our methods in contexts that include the practices taking place as algorithms are envisioned and designed to map the entire social life of *an algorithm*, these early findings indicate that embedding ideals and values to algorithms disguise algorithmic potentials and limitations as sensible rather than logical, which helps control the narratives of appropriation and adoption. This raises concerns about how the ideals and values that are used to guide the design of principled algorithms can be easily replaced as soon as the technologies are deployed. Therefore, focusing on how algorithms are imbued and removed of ideals and values is relevant not only for scrutinising the ways in which researchers race to replace technical ideals with moral ones as a strategy to enable a more humane use of algorithmic technologies [Morley et al., 2021]. In addition, more attention needs to be placed on examining how the ideals and values which we rely upon to talk about, explain, introduce, and imagine algorithms can lead to changes in social and cultural practices that unfold outside the relational, spatial and temporal boundaries where humans and algorithms interact.

7 Conclusion

Through an empirical account of the social life of the *Bitcoin algorithm*, this late-breaking research contributes a novel approach to extend ethnographies of algorithms beyond the spatial and temporal boundaries where humans and algorithms interact. Our findings show that notions of algorithms and positions towards algorithm-driven technologies are shaped not only by human-algorithm interactions but also by engagements with the embedded ideals and values within algorithms. These negotiations are influenced by the contextual factors and situations in which they occur, wherein the values and ideals inherent in practices and algorithms continually shape one another.

Consequently, the deliberate socialisation of a carefully curated understanding of *an algorithm* led the residents of El Zonte to adopt a position towards Bitcoin technology based on their perception of its transformative potential rather than solely on the technical attributes of Bitcoin services. This research underscores the need to examine further how the principles, ideals, and values underpinning algorithm design can influence individuals' comprehension and adoption of algorithm-driven technologies.

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References

1. Appadurai, Arjun, ed. *The social life of things: Commodities in cultural perspective*. Cambridge University Press, 1988.
2. Benjamin, Ruha. "Race after technology: Abolitionist tools for the new Jim code." (2020): 1-3.
3. Bandura, Albert, and Richard H. Walters. *Social learning theory*. Vol. 1. Prentice Hall: Englewood cliffs, 1977.
4. Bishop, Sophie. "Managing visibility on YouTube through algorithmic gossip." *New media & society* 21.11-12 (2019): 2589-2606.
5. Bucher, Taina. "The algorithmic imaginary: Exploring the ordinary affects of Facebook algorithms." *Information, communication & society* 20.1 (2017): 30-44.
6. Büchi, Moritz, et al. "Making sense of algorithmic profiling: user perceptions on Facebook." *Information, Communication & Society* (2021): 1-17.
7. Cave, Stephen, Kanta Dihal, and Sarah Dillon, eds. *AI narratives: A history of imaginative thinking about intelligent machines*. Oxford University Press, 2020.
8. Crawford, Kate, and Ryan Calo. "There is a blind spot in AI research." *Nature* 538.7625 (2016): 311-313.
9. Diakopoulos, Nicholas. "Algorithmic accountability: Journalistic investigation of computational power structures." *Digital journalism* 3.3 (2015): 398-415.
10. Dourish, Paul. "Algorithms and their others: Algorithmic culture in context." *Big Data & Society* 3.2 (2016): 2053951716665128.
11. Dunbar, Robin IM. "Gossip in evolutionary perspective." *Review of general psychology* 8.2 (2004): 100-110.
12. Eslami, Motahhare, et al. "First I like it, then I hide it: Folk Theories of Social Feeds." *Proceedings of the 2016 CHI conference on human factors in computing systems*. 2016.
13. Eubanks, Virginia. *Automating inequality: How high-tech tools profile, police, and punish the poor*. St. Martin's Press, 2018.
14. Fournier, Marcel. *Marcel Mauss*. Princeton University Press, 2005.
15. Gillespie, Tarleton. "The relevance of algorithms." *Media technologies: Essays on communication, materiality, and society* 167.2014 (2014): 167.
16. Gillespie, Tarleton. *Custodians of the Internet: Platforms, content moderation, and the hidden decisions that shape social media*. Yale University Press, 2018.
17. Gran, Anne-Britt, Peter Booth, and Taina Bucher. "To be or not to be algorithm aware: a question of a new digital divide?." *Information, Communication & Society* 24.12 (2021): 1779-1796.
18. Gunn, Wendy, Ton Otto, and Rachel Charlotte Smith, eds. *Design anthropology: theory and practice*. Taylor & Francis, 2013.
19. Kitchin, Rob, and Tracey Lauriault. "Towards critical data studies: Charting and unpacking data assemblages and their work." (2014).
20. Kitchin, Rob, and Martin Dodge. *Code/space: Software and everyday life*. Mit Press, 2014.
21. Kleinberg, Jon, et al. "Human decisions and machine predictions." *The quarterly journal of economics* 133.1 (2018): 237-293.
22. Kitchin, Rob. "Thinking critically about and researching algorithms." *Information, communication & society* 20.1 (2017): 14-29.
23. Kopytoff, Igor. "The cultural biography of things: commoditization as process." *The social life of things: Commodities in cultural perspective* 68 (1986): 70-73.
24. Lomborg, Stine, and Patrick Heiberg Kapsch. "Decoding algorithms." *Media, Culture & Society* 42.5 (2020): 745-761.

25. Marcus, George E. "Ethnography in/of the world system: The emergence of multi-sited ethnography." *Annual review of anthropology* 24.1 (1995): 95-117.
26. Mehlman, Jeffrey. "The" floating signifier": from Lévi-Strauss to Lacan." *Yale French Studies* (1972): 10-37.
27. Mittelstadt, Brent, Chris Russell, and Sandra Wachter. "Explaining explanations in AI." *Proceedings of the conference on fairness, accountability, and transparency*. 2019.
28. Morley, Jessica, et al. "Operationalising AI ethics: barriers, enablers and next steps." *AI & SOCIETY* (2021): 1-13.
29. Nakamoto, Satoshi. "Bitcoin: A peer-to-peer electronic cash system." *Decentralized business review* (2008): 21260.
30. Noble, Safiya Umoja. "Algorithms of oppression." *Algorithms of oppression*. New York University Press, 2018.
31. Pasquale, Frank. *The black box society: The secret algorithms that control money and information*. Harvard University Press, 2015.
32. Rabinow, Paul, et al. "Designs for an Anthropology of the Contemporary." *Designs for an Anthropology of the Contemporary*. Duke University Press, 2008.
33. Ruckenstein, Minna, and Julia Granroth. "Algorithms, advertising and the intimacy of surveillance." *Journal of Cultural Economy* 13.1 (2020): 12-24.
34. Sandvig, Christian, et al. "Auditing algorithms: Research methods for detecting discrimination on internet platforms." *Data and discrimination: converting critical concerns into productive inquiry* 22.2014 (2014): 4349-4357.
35. Schellewald, Andreas. "Theorizing "stories about algorithms" as a mechanism in the formation and maintenance of algorithmic imaginaries." *Social Media+ Society* 8.1 (2022): 20563051221077025.
36. Seaver, Nick. "Algorithms as culture: Some tactics for the ethnography of algorithmic systems." *Big data & society* 4.2 (2017): 2053951717738104.
37. Seaver, Nick. "What should an anthropology of algorithms do?." *Cultural anthropology* 33.3 (2018): 375-385.
38. Smith, Rachel Charlotte, and Mette Gislev Kjærsgaard. "Design Anthropology in Participatory Design." *ID&A Interaction design & architecture* (s) 26 (2015): 73-80.
39. Smith, Rachel Charlotte, et al. "Design Anthropological Futures." (2016).
40. Thomson, Alistair. "Making the most of memories: the empirical and subjective value of oral history." *Transactions of the Royal Historical Society* 9 (1999): 291-301.
41. Tunstall, Elizabeth Dori. "Decolonizing design innovation: Design anthropology, critical anthropology, and indigenous knowledge." *Design Anthropology*. Routledge, 2020. 232-250.
42. Varga-Atkins, Tünde, and Mark O'Brien. "From drawings to diagrams: Maintaining researcher control during graphic elicitation in qualitative interviews." *International Journal of Research & Method in Education* 32.1 (2009): 53-67.